

Evaluation of real-time global flood modeling with satellite surface inundation observations from SMAP

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ABSTRACT

Improving flood modeling accuracy is crucial for real-time flood monitoring and early warning systems. Knowing the sources, patterns and driving factors of model uncertainty aids the development of more accurate flood predictions. This study investigates the consistency of two global flood inundation products, i.e., the Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP) satellite based fractional water (F_w) cover and the Global Flood Monitoring System (GFMS) modeled flood inundation. Using Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) as the indicator of the SMAP-GFMS model consistency, this research documents the spatial and temporal patterns of the correlations between the two flood products, and investigates factors affecting these relationships, including climate, land cover, hydrology and terrain distributions. Results reveal that globally, 64% locations have moderate to strong SMAP-GFMS correlation ($r \geq 0.4$). Locations that are dry and have low biomass and high seasonal flood variability tend to have high correlation; for example, 47% locations with $r \geq 0.4$ occur in tropical and arid climate zones, and 43% locations with $r \geq 0.4$ are observed in *Barren*, *Evergreen Broadleaf Forest*, *Grasslands*, *Open Shrubland* and *Savannahs*. Also, larger rivers have higher correlation, and in each Strahler stream order there are 60% to 65% locations having $r \geq 0.4$. Larger watersheds show higher SMAP-GFMS consistency in particular watersheds between 1000 and 40,000 km². Regions with greater urban infrastructure tend to have lower correlation, while locations with lower elevations and relatively flat topography have higher SMAP-GFMS consistency. This study indicates that GFMS and SMAP provide complementary information on surface water storage variations influencing precipitation driven runoff and flooding, which may enable enhanced global flood predictions.

1. Introduction

The uncertainty in global flood modeling has been a serious impediment to widespread use of these models in operational flood response and disaster management activities. An acceptable and well-documented confidence level of available flood information from various providers is critical to better inform the decision-making process by end users, such as the International Red Cross and Red Crescent, and the UN World Food Program (Wu et al., 2014; Alfieri et al., 2018). Quantifying and analyzing the spatial-temporal patterns and mechanisms of inconsistency in various modeled global flood results against

observational benchmarks can help to verify and improve model performance, but is challenging due to a lack of reliable flood observations at global scale.

The Global Flood Monitoring System (GFMS), as one of the real-time flood information providers and active contributors of the Global Flood Partnership (Alfieri et al., 2018), has been widely accessed by agencies and organizations worldwide (Wu et al., 2014). The GFMS routinely provides global flood monitoring at 1/8th degree resolution every 3 h, using hydrological models informed by satellite-based precipitation inputs. The NASA Tropical Rainfall Measurement Mission (TRMM) provided high quality quasi-global (50°S–50°N) satellite based

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precipitation observations, at 3-hourly intervals and quarter-degree spatial resolution from 1998 to 2015 (Huffman et al., 2010). GFMS utilizes the Dominant River Tracing-Routing Integrated with VIC Environment (DRIVE) model (Wu et al., 2011, 2012, 2014) to predict hydrological variables over the global domain, including streamflow, flood intensity and inundation. Wu et al. (2014) performed the validation of the global flood system and the DRIVE model using observed river discharge data from a global distribution of 1121 GRDC river gauges (Wu et al., 2014), and 2086 flood events compiled by the Dartmouth Flood Observatory (Wu et al., 2014). Uncertainty in the GFMS flood model due to contributing uncertainty in the satellite based precipitation records used as model inputs was recently investigated over the mid-sized Iowa-Cedar river basin located in the central USA (Wu et al., 2017). Similar studies on evaluating the impacts of uncertainty in satellite precipitation on hydrological modeling and flood prediction have been conducted by previous researchers such as Beck et al. (2017), and Maggioni and Massari (2018). However, these evaluation work has limitations, particularly in the limited spatial coverage of the observational data used for model assessment (i.e., only observations at sparsely distributed locations were investigated). The Global Precipitation Measurement (GPM) mission was inaugurated in February 2014 as follow-on to TRMM and provides next generation satellite global precipitation estimates with higher spatial (5–15 km) and temporal (0.5–3 h) resolution, and better accuracy. Satellite global precipitation observations from GPM remain crucial for real-time and high accuracy global flood modeling systems, such as the GFMS (Hou et al., 2014; Kirschbaum et al., 2016). Further validation of the GFMS against independent global observations representing key model parameters provides an effective means for establishing GFMS performance and confidence in the derived flood information, and potentially improving the model predictions, including optimizing model parameterization by calibrating against suitable observations. The GFMS predicts streamflow (discharge) and surface water storage from a hydrological runoff and routing model. The GFMS model utilizes multiple input data, including TRMM Multi-satellite Precipitation Analysis (TMPA) precipitation, air temperature, wind speed, topography, hydrographic parameters (flow direction, flow distance, drainage area, channel, river order etc.), soil and vegetation conditions. Satellite based observations of surface water inundation extent are currently available over the global domain and provide suitable accuracy, spatial resolution and temporal fidelity for evaluating similar GFMS derived inundation dynamics, i.e., the routed runoff variable representing the water depth above dry ground calculated by the DRIVE model, which is also the basis for flood event detection and flood intensity derivation in the GFMS (Wu et al., 2014).

The NASA Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP) satellite was launched in January 2015 and provides global operational retrievals of near surface soil moisture and landscape freeze-thaw status benefiting from L-band (1.41 GHz) passive microwave sensitivity to surface and soil moisture conditions. The SMAP radiometer brightness temperature (T_b) and soil moisture retrievals are mapped to a 36-km resolution global grid similar to the ~40-km native sensor footprint (Entekhabi et al., 2010); these data are also produced in a finer 9-km resolution global grid format derived through spatial enhancement of the SMAP antenna temperatures using a Backus-Gilbert optimal interpolation approach (Chan et al., 2018). The relatively low latency (~12 h) between the SMAP observations and posting of the operational T_b products is well suited for near real-time applications (Entekhabi et al., 2010). Du et al. (2018) developed a new global observational record of surface water inundation dynamics using the SMAP T_b record to detect surface water, while minimizing the contaminating influence of overlying vegetation cover, temperature, soil and atmospheric moisture on the surface water signal using ancillary land parameter information from overlapping AMSR-2 (Advanced Microwave Scanning Radiometer-2) observations (Du et al., 2017). The SMAP fractional water (F_w) retrieval represents the spatial proportion of standing water within the sensor footprint and

is derived with approximately 3-day temporal fidelity in both 36-km and 9-km global grid formats in support of SMAP mission applications objectives for improving global flood assessments. Such fractional water information from an independent approach is highly valuable for further evaluating the GFMS performance in flood modeling at global scale. The SMAP F_w record adopted in this study shows robust accuracy and performance according to the validation by Du et al. (2018), which provides the justification for using it as a suitable global observational benchmark for evaluating GFMS surface inundation dynamics, although it may not be considered as the truth.

This study is motivated to confront and verify hydrological model-based flood assessments against independent global observational benchmarks, through quantifying the concurrence (at the same time) and consistency (over time) of derived land surface water dynamics between the different retrieval approaches. We compared the SMAP-based F_w product (Du et al., 2018) and GFMS flood modeling results (routed runoff) (Wu et al., 2014) from June 2015 to May 2016, which spans the first year of SMAP operations. The comparison provides further evaluation of GFMS flood prediction performance with a particular emphasis on evaluating the component DRIVE model performance. This evaluation also provides a means for further evaluating the consistency and quality of the SMAP F_w product against similar estimates from an advanced numerical DRIVE process model, which may lead to potential improvements in the land parameter retrievals.

The rest of this paper is organized as following. First, the methodology to compare SMAP-GFMS results is introduced in Section 2, including data processing, analysis of correlations and their spatial and temporal distributions. Section 3 gives a detailed analysis of the spatial and seasonal patterns of the SMAP-GFMS correlations, and the relationships between the correlation patterns and potential influencing factors including climate, land cover, hydrology (stream order, flow accumulation), and terrain (elevation and slope). Finally, Section 4 provides a summary and concluding remarks based on the study results.

2. Methods

The overall methodological design for this study is shown in Fig. 1. The strength of the relationships between the SMAP and GFMS model results (i.e., consistency), and the influence of various physical and environmental factors on these relations is evaluated using the Pearson's correlation coefficient, r . As SMAP and GFMS have different spatial and temporal resolutions, the GFMS data are transformed to a 9-km by 9-km grid resolution consistent with the SMAP 9-km F_w data record. Here, the spatially enhanced 9-km grid F_w record was selected for this study rather than the baseline 36-km F_w record (Du et al., 2018) because it is closer in scale to the GFMS operational global grid. Both GFMS and SMAP F_w records were also temporally aggregated to a monthly time scale for this study to emphasize seasonal climate patterns rather than more transient variations due to weather. The r value for the correlation analysis (Fig. 1) is computed between monthly SMAP and GFMS F_w time series ($n = 12$) on a per grid cell basis. The spatial and temporal patterns of the SMAP-GFMS correlation are then detected, and the relationships between r and the five variables (climate, land cover, Strahler river orders, upstream drainage area flow accumulation and terrain) are investigated.

The GFMS runoff and SMAP F_w based r values were first grouped into four categorical bins by correlation sign and strength: $-1.0 \leq r < 0.0$ (negative), $0.0 \leq r < 0.4$ (weak, positive), $0.4 \leq r < 0.7$ (moderate to strong, positive), and $r \geq 0.7$ (strong, p -value < 0.01 , two-tailed probability).

Additionally, a two-dimensional matrix was constructed for each of the five influencing factors, where the factor's values and the correlation bins are the matrix axis', and each matrix entry is the relative frequency at a certain factor value and a certain r bin; for example, for the land cover factor, an entry value may indicate how many permanent wetland cells have strong positive GFMS-SMAP correlation ($r \geq 0.7$).

Fig. 1. The schema of SMAP-GFMS global comparison.

For each factor, the discussion will be conducted with two types of analyses. In the first analysis, for each matrix entry, the number of cells is divided by the total number of cells in the global GFMS study domain, i.e., the relative frequency of a factor value in a given correlation bin. And the second analysis divides each matrix entry by the total number of cells having the same factor value across all correlation bins, i.e., the relative frequency of r -values with respect to cells across different values of a factor. The first analysis describes “how the r values are distributed by the associated factor value” (e.g., of all available cells in the global domain, 0.3% of cells are in *permanent wetlands* having $r \geq 0.7$), while the second aims to answer whether “there is any difference in r -values across different factor values?” (e.g., 76.3% cells of *permanent wetlands* have $r \geq 0.7$). This section organizes the discussion into these two types of analyses.

2.1. SMAP F_w algorithm and data

The SMAP observations are well suited for detecting land surface fractional water (F_w) cover and surface soil moisture conditions due to the enhanced ability of lower frequency L-band (1.4 GHz) microwave sensors to detect land surface emissions in the presence of vegetation cover (Chan et al., 2016). To estimate F_w from SMAP brightness temperature (T_b) observations of mixed microwave emissions from water, vegetation and soil, a look-up table (LUT) was first established to provide reference L-band emissivities for land and water global endmembers under a range of soil, vegetation and surface temperature conditions. The SMAP 36-km and 9-km F_w retrievals were obtained on a per grid cell basis by computing the deviations of SMAP observed emissivity from a pure land reference value normalized by the emissivity difference of pure land and water global endmembers. For both the LUT and F_w retrieval process, the surface conditions were defined using an ancillary global Land Parameter Data Record (LPDR) derived from AMSR (Advanced Microwave Scanning Radiometer) multi-frequency T_b observations and GEOS-5 soil temperatures (Du et al., 2017). The quality of the F_w retrievals showed more uncertainty in areas with higher vegetation biomass levels, and no retrievals were made for grid cells identified as being predominantly frozen, dominated by large water bodies ($F_w > 50\%$), or with significant Radio Frequency Interference (RFI) indicated from the AMSR LPDR or SMAP soil moisture products (Chan et al., 2016). The detailed algorithm description and global performance assessment for the SMAP F_w retrieval is provided elsewhere (Du et al., 2018), while differences in performance between the F_w 9-km grid record used in this study relative to the baseline 36-km F_w global record is provided below.

A 36-km SMAP global F_w data set previously derived using SMAP L1C T_b data showed strong correspondence with a static MOD44W (Carroll et al., 2009) global water map ($R = 0.85$, p -value < 0.001 ; RMSD = 0.064; wet bias 0.032) and captured significant global

inundation seasonal variations and 2015–2016 ENSO-driven regional flooding (Du et al., 2018). For this study, a similar F_w algorithm was applied to the SMAP spatially enhanced L1C T_b record (L1CTBE, Chaubell et al., 2018) for generating SMAP F_w retrievals over a finer 9-km resolution global grid. The baseline 36-km and enhanced 9-km F_w algorithms differ mainly in the definition of LUT pure water emissivity, which was calculated using theoretical models and SMAP observations for the respective 36-km and 9-km retrieval approaches (Du et al., 2016; Du et al., 2018). The 9-km F_w data set used for this study has enhanced spatial resolution gridding relative to the baseline 36-km product while preserving similar performance indicated by comparing the SMAP 9-km grid mean annual composite F_w results against the MOD44W global water body map ($R = 0.82$, p -value < 0.001 ; RMSD = 0.056; bias = 0.003). The annual mean values of the SMAP 9-km F_w data are highly correlated to the corresponding 36-km results ($R = 0.93$) but show a small dry bias (-0.03) due to differences in the retrieval algorithms and L1CTB[E] T_b records used as model inputs.

2.2. Data processing

Data processing aims to resolve the differences in the spatial and temporal resolution of the SMAP and GFMS model results. The SMAP data are retrieved from http://files.ntsg.umd.edu/data/SMAP_FW_9KM (accessed June 22, 2017) (Du et al., 2016). The SMAP F_w data were derived over the global land domain with approximately 3-day mean temporal fidelity consistent with other SMAP observations, and then temporally composited to the monthly time step. The resulting F_w record represents the monthly mean fractional spatial coverage of standing water within each 9-km grid cell over the global domain. The monthly F_w record between June 2015 and May 2016 was used for this study, representing the initial year of SMAP operations. The F_w data projection is in a Global EASE-GRID Version 2 format (Brodzik et al., 2014) consistent with other SMAP products, while the product geographical coverage extends from 90°N–90°S and 180°W–180°E. GFMS routed runoff data between June 2015 and May 2016 are from the real-time Global Flood Monitoring System (<http://flood.umd.edu>, accessed June 22, 2017). The GFMS data are recorded in WGS84 representing surface water storage (unit: mm) variations every 3 h at 1/8th degree (~12 km) grid resolution, while the GFMS geographical coverage extends 50°N–50°S and 180°W–180°E. This study analyzes the SMAP-GFMS correlations over their respective coverage comprising the intervals 50°N–50°S and 180°W–180°E.

To compare the SMAP F_w record with integrated GFMS routed runoff data, the spatial and temporal resolution of GFMS routed runoff data are adjusted to match the SMAP composited monthly record. First the 3-hour GFMS data are averaged by month. That is, at each grid cell (i, j) for a specific month, the monthly GFMS surface water storage is computed from the 3-hour GFMS surface water storage values as:

Fig. 2. Distance-based resampling method vs proportion-based resampling used for the GFMS and SMAP cell comparisons.

$$averaged_routed_runoff_month = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n runoff_i}{n}$$

where $runoff_i$ is the routed runoff for a given 3-hour time period, and n is the total number of 3-hour periods within a month. For example, for April 2015, n is $(30 \text{ days}) \times (24 \text{ h})/\text{day}/(3 \text{ h}) = 240$; whereas $n = 248$ for May 2015.

After converting the temporal resolution of the GFMS data, it is resampled to have the same spatial resolution as the SMAP 9-km Fw data. In image processing, the most common resampling methods are nearest-neighbor, bi-linear interpolation or cubic convolution. However, because SMAP and GFMS data have different projections and spatial resolutions, these resampling methods may reduce the quality of the transformed data due to the following reasons. The GFMS runoff grid cells are not squares once they are projected to the Global EASE-GRID format, and the resampling methods (e.g., bi-linear interpolation) are based on the distance between each neighboring cell to the cell being interpolated as the weight in order to incorporate neighboring grid cells (i.e., distance-based resampling). However, water storage in a grid cell is not the weighted sum of other cells. Therefore, this study adopts a proportion-based approach for better accuracy (Fig. 2).

First, the SMAP and GFMS grid cells are converted into polygons with the cell values as the polygon attribute. GFMS polygons are projected from WGS84 to Global EASE-GRID Version 2 format to produce a set of irregular shaped polygons ($g_i, i = 1, 2 \dots, n$). Each SMAP cell is then spatially overlaid with the collocated GFMS polygons, which are segmented by the coarser SMAP grid. Only those GFMS segments within the SMAP cell are aggregated ($g_{ij}, j = 1, 2 \dots, m$, where m indicates how many GFMS polygons contribute to the SMAP cell); g_{ij} has a geographical area (km^2) denoted as s_{ij} , while each original GFMS polygon (g_i) has area a_i and routed runoff value o_i . For each GFMS segment g_{ij} , the ratio $r_{ij} = s_{ij}/a_i$ is the area proportion of each segment to the original GFMS polygon. Then, the routed runoff value for the segment s_{ij} is $o_{ij} = r_{ij} * o_i$. Finally, the routed GFMS runoff value for a given SMAP cell is the sum of s_{ij} within the cell. When a cell has no SMAP data, the corresponding GFMS cell is also left empty. In this way, the GFMS routed runoff water is re-distributed to a SMAP cell based on the proportion of geographical area. For the convenience of spatial analysis, the transformed GFMS and SMAP polygons are converted back to grid cells.

2.3. Correlation between SMAP and GFMS

The GFMS routed runoff data were spatially adjusted to be

consistent with the SMAP 9 km Fw data, while the temporal aggregation of both data records resulted in twelve pairs of SMAP and GFMS monthly data for each grid cell over the GFMS global domain. The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was then computed using the paired monthly data for each grid cell with a hypothesis of linear correlation between SMAP and GFMS data. About 15% of the grid cells in the SMAP monthly data record have missing values due to screening of frozen surface conditions or grid cells with large static water bodies ($Fw > 50\%$). Hulley et al. (2013) investigated the minimal sample size needed for correlation analysis and found that six to sixteen data pairs are required to achieve certain level of Type I error (the probability to reject the null hypothesis), Type II error (the probability failing to reject the null hypothesis), and the expected correlation coefficient (i.e., 0.4 for this study) that can be correctly determined; and with ten data pairs Zhao and Running (2010) determined the correlation between the global terrestrial net primary production and global atmospheric CO_2 . Therefore, the correlation coefficients were only derived for cells with six or more months (pairs) of valid data, while most correlation analysis in this study are based on samples with twelve SMAP-GFMS pairs.

The Pearson correlation coefficient r detects whether the two variables follow a linear relationship (strength and direction) and requires the normality of the variables. This paper does not test the linear relationship and normality directly, instead it confirms the SMAP-GFMS correlations with a different correlation indicator, Distance Correlation ($dcor$) (Szekely and Rizzo, 2009). In other words, if r and $dcor$ has linear relationship, r is appropriate to identify the association between two variables. Distance Correlation is a method to evaluate the linear and nonlinear correlation between two variables (Kosorok, 2009; Simon and Tibshirani, 2011). Given two paired variables (X_i, Y_i), $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, the n by n pairwise distance matrix for X_i and for Y_i can be computed as:

$$a_{k,i} = \|X_k - X_i\|, k, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

$$b_{k,i} = \|Y_k - Y_i\|, k, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

where $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the Euclidean distance between k and i . The doubly centered distances are computed as:

$$A_{k,i} = a_{k,i} - \bar{a}_k - \bar{a}_i + \bar{a}.$$

$$B_{k,i} = b_{k,i} - \bar{b}_k - \bar{b}_i + \bar{b}.$$

where \bar{a}_k and \bar{b}_k are the k -th row mean in the pairwise distance matrices, \bar{a}_i and \bar{b}_i are the i -th column mean, and \bar{a} and \bar{b} are the grand mean of the pairwise distance matrices of the two variables. Then the distance covariance is defined as

$$dCov^2(X, Y) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^n A_{k,i} B_{k,i}$$

The distance variance of variable X ($dVar(X)$) and Y ($dVar(Y)$) can be computed in a similar way as the covariance except that the two variables are identical. Then the distance correlation between X and Y is defined as:

$$dCor(X, Y) = \frac{dCov(X, Y)}{\sqrt{dVar(X)dVar(Y)}}$$

The value of $dCor$ is between 0 and 1, with $dCor = 0$ if X and Y are independent, and $dCor = 1$ if they are fully dependent (linear or non-linear relationship). For a cell where r and $dCor$ have a linear association, the Pearson's r is considered appropriate to capture the SMAP-GFMS correlation.

2.4. Temporal dynamics between SMAP and GFMS

The routed runoff is the water depth above the dry ground according to the calculation from the kinematic wave routing scheme deployed in the DRIVE flood model. Temporal lags may occur between a GFMS detected monthly flood event and associated changes in Fw cover observed from SMAP due to associated differences between precipitation-driven catchment runoff routing and SMAP retrieved surface water storage dynamics. A lag operation in this study is necessary in some cases for a better temporal matching up between the two products under various conditions. For example, the lag can be due to shorter model residence time for water moving through river basins as a result of inappropriate parameterization of drainage network, relative coarse resolution precipitation input, and uncertainty in precipitation input etc. Meanwhile, on the remote sensing end, the SMAP Fw retrievals tend to be biased high in inundation estimation in areas with saturated soil which also requires a lag of model results for a better time matching. Therefore, the correlation between GFMS and temporally lagged SMAP Fw data was also computed for each grid cell to analyze the consistency between the two products over time and the temporal lag required to produce optimal agreement for each grid cell. For example, for a 0-month shift, the model results are paired as June 2015 (GFMS) vs June 2015 (SMAP), July 2015 (GFMS) vs July 2015 (SMAP), etc., for up to 12 paired data points per grid cell; for a 1-month shift, the pairs are June 2015 (GFMS) vs July 2015 (SMAP), July 2015 (GFMS) vs August 2015 (SMAP), etc., for up to 11 paired data points.

2.5. Spatial pattern of the SMAP and GFMS model correlation

A spatial cluster and outlier analysis, Local Moran's I_i (Anselin, 1995), was employed to clarify the SMAP-GFMS correlation pattern. Given a set of locations (grid cells), the SMAP-GFMS correlation r -value at each cell is denoted as r_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, where n is the total number of cells, and the Euclidean distance between two cells is $d_{i,j}$. The Local Moran's I_i statistic is then computed for each cell as:

$$I_i = \frac{r_i - \bar{r}}{S_i^2} \times \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^n w_{i,j} (r_j - \bar{r}),$$

where $\bar{r} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n r_j}{n}$, $S_i^2 = \frac{\sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^n (r_j - \bar{r})^2}{n-1}$, and $w_{i,j}$ is defined as the inverse distance ($1/d_{i,j}$) indicating the spatial interaction between i and j which implies that closer cells have stronger interaction or influence than more distant cells.

For each grid cell, I_i reflects the spatial relationship between a given cell and other cells weighted by their spatial interaction ($w_{i,j}$). A positive I_i value indicates that a given cell value is similar to spatially surrounding cells, i.e., the cell is part of a spatial cluster. The cluster is identified as a regional "hot spot" if it represents a cluster of high r values, or a "cold spot" when the cluster has low r values. A negative I_i indicates that the cell has a dissimilar value than the surrounding cells,

and is therefore a spatial outlier.

2.6. Environmental factors influencing SMAP and GFMS model consistency

Using the SMAP-GFMS correlation r as an indicator of model consistency, it is expected that the correlation has spatial and temporal (instead of random) patterns that reflect variations in geographical context, where there might be different constraints and associated performance regarding the hydrological modeling and satellite retrieval of surface inundation. We analyzed the spatial pattern of the correlations between GFMS runoff and SMAP Fw , in relation to five environmental factors potentially affecting model and satellite retrieval performance and their relationships. These geospatial factors are climate, land cover, Strahler stream order, basin flow accumulation, and terrain complexity. All of these factors are used as ancillary inputs to compute routed runoff in the GFMS model, while land cover and terrain conditions also influence SMAP Fw retrieval performance (Du et al., 2018).

We used a Köppen global climate zone classification to evaluate the relative impact of climate variability on the SMAP-GFMS correlations. The climate zones data were downloaded from <https://people.eng.unimelb.edu.au/mpeel/koppen.html> (accessed July 12, 2017) with 0.1-degree spatial resolution, and then re-projected from the native geographic projection to the 9-km Global EASE-GRID Version 2 projection grid.

The MODIS 5-minute IGBP land cover (MCD12Q1 circa 2012) map (Friedl et al., 2010) is presented in Fig. 3 and was used to evaluate SMAP-GFMS correlations across different land cover categories. The land cover map was resampled from the native MODIS data to have the same spatial resolution as the SMAP data, so that the SMAP-GFMS r -value for each grid cell is associated with a single dominant land cover type derived from the underlying finer scale land cover map.

This study also investigates hydrological constraints (stream and watershed) that may affect GFMS performance. Streams recorded in Strahler orders are created with the Dominant River Tracing (DRT) upscaling algorithm (Wu et al., 2011). The Strahler orders are coded from 1 to 8, where 1 indicates the smallest streams and order 8 represents the major rivers. The per grid cell relationship between the SMAP-GFMS correlations and the associated Strahler stream order of the cell is summarized in the next section.

In addition to the stream order data, flow accumulation is calculated as the total catchment area of water flow to a given cell. Thus flow accumulation can be used to define watersheds, which, like Strahler stream order, is also an input variable of the GFMS-DRIVE model (Wu et al., 2014). A cell with high flow accumulation indicates a large watershed, where the contributing watersheds are classified into five different sized categories from 0–999, 1000–9999, 10,000–99,999, 100,000–499,999, to > 500,000 km² over the global domain. Here, higher SMAP-GFMS correlations are expected to be associated with larger flow accumulation (watershed size) owing to generally greater abundance of surface water and runoff in larger watersheds that can be more easily resolved from relatively coarse global satellite observations and GFMS model simulations.

The elevation and slope data are retrieved from the HydroSHEDS global hydrography dataset using the DRT algorithms (Lehner et al., 2008; Wu et al., 2012) and evaluated to reveal the potential influence of terrain heterogeneity on the SMAP-GFMS correlation. To measure the combined effect of elevation and slope on the correlations, we computed the Multi Resolution index of Valley Bottom Flatness (MRVBF) (Gallant and Dowling, 2003). The MRVBF measures the relative flatness and lowness at a location, and thus determines valley bottoms that are characteristically flat, low lying and spatially extensive. Larger MRVBF values indicate cells with generally flatter and lower topography, consistent with valley bottom locations. The open source system SAGA (www.saga-gis.org) is used to compute the MRVBF index for each cell within the global domain. The resulting indices are then grouped into seven general MRVBF classes, where higher MRVBF class numbers

Fig. 3. MODIS IGBP land cover map (Friedl et al., 2010).

Fig. 4. The global MRVBF categories ranging from class 0 for mountainous terrain with steep slopes and high elevations, to class 6 for flat and low elevation grid cells consistent with valley bottom locations.

indicate more consistent valley bottom characteristics (Fig. 4).

3. Results and analyses

3.1. SMAP-GFMS correlation in space and time

In order to test the linearity of the SMAP-GFMS correlation so that the Person's correlation coefficient r can indicate the SMAP-GFMS correlation, distance correlation analysis is conducted at each cell using the 12 pairs of data. The $dcor$ at each grid cell is computed and the summary is provided in Fig. 5 and Table 1. Linear regression analysis is conducted between r and $dcor$ at each cell. When r is positive, the regression analysis presents $R^2 = 0.86$, p -value = 0.0, and when r is negative, the regression presents $R^2 = 0.66$, p -value = 0.0. The strong linear correlation between r and $dcor$ supports the use of r as an indicator of the correlation between SMAP and GFMS results. It also indicates that SMAP-GFMS presents linear relationship.

Fig. 6 and Table 1 provide a summary of the r -values between GFMS

runoff and SMAP F_w records over the global GFMS domain (50°N-50°S, and 180°W-180°E). Approximately 29.6% of grid cells within the domain have a strong positive SMAP-GFMS correlation ($r \geq 0.7$); 34.3% of cells have moderate to strong correlation ($0.4 \leq r < 0.7$), while a large majority (90.5%) of the global domain shows a positive relationship between the two records ($r > 0$). When the significance (p -values) of the SMAP-GFMS correlations are considered, 49.2% of the cells have p -value < 0.1 , 16.8% cells with p -value < 0.05 (moderate), 13.3% with p -value < 0.01 (strong), and 9.3% cells have very strong significant level (p -value < 0.001). As illustrated in Fig. 8(a) and (c), of the 63.9% of cells with $r \geq 0.4$, 31.1% show the highest correspondence between GFMS runoff and SMAP F_w variations occurring within the same monthly period, with no apparent temporal lag; whereas 11.6% of cells show a 1-month lag, 9.2% show a 2-month lag, and 12.0% of cells show a 3-month lag having the best correlations.

The global distribution of grid cells with $r \geq 0$ and $r \geq 0.4$ (p -value < 0.1 , two-tailed probability) with respect to the temporal shifts between GFMS routed runoff and SMAP F_w records is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 5. The distance correlation at each grid cell.

The horizontal axis indicates the shift by month (0 to 7 months) as explained above, and the vertical axis is the percent of grid cells from the global domain with $r \geq 0$ and $r \geq 0.4$ at each time shift. The grid cell correlations show a general decline as the temporal lag increases from 0 to 3 months, while further degradation of the correlations becomes less over longer temporal lags. These results indicate that a given SMAP F_w flood event may be unrelated to GFMS runoff occurring more than three months prior to the event, which can be explained by the fact that river basin characteristics other than direct precipitation driven runoff can also affect surface water storage dynamics within the basin extending up to about three-month lag (Wu et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2018). We computed per grid cell correlations between GFMS runoff and SMAP F_w for successive F_w monthly lags ranging from 0 to 3 months. We then mapped the highest r -value and corresponding significance (p -value) of the relationship (Fig. 8a, b), and temporal lag value (0, 1, 2, and 3 months) with the highest correspondence as shown in Fig. 8c. The following discussion is based on the result presented in Fig. 8.

As shown in Fig. 8, the ~3-month temporal lag over central Australia is consistent with a characteristic delay between monsoon driven rainfall in the north and delayed runoff flows and filling of dry playa lake beds and seasonal wetlands in the central region (Xie et al., 2016; Zhao et al., 2017). Similar temporal lag patterns also show up in other semi-arid areas, including South Western North America, Southern Africa, and the South American sub-tropics. Other areas show more concurrent changes in SMAP F_w and GFMS runoff, including the South Eastern United States, African Sahel and the Indian subcontinent; these areas are characterized by low to moderate topography with widespread and relatively well defined surface wetting and inundation changes from seasonal rainfall.

To investigate the temporal lag between SMAP and GFMS data, a single location near Gurupa, Brazil at the lower stream of Amazon River is selected. The temporal lag is provided in Fig. 9, where the SMAP-GFMS correlation coefficient is 0.55 (p -value: 0.06) without considering

temporal lag and is 0.91 (p -value: 0.0002) with a 2-month temporal lag. This is attributed to the temporal lag between F_w and observed river discharge due to the lag between upstream rainfall and the downstream river gauge flood pulse (see the supplementary file, Du et al., 2018); however, GFMS accounts for the runoff lag time given the per-cell (rather than whole basin) comparison here. Similarly, mountain areas such as Sierra Nevada and Andes show concurrent F_w and runoff changes driven by seasonal snowmelt, which also likely has significant F_w gaps due to seasonal frozen conditions.

The result of the spatial cluster and outlier analysis of r values is provided in Fig. 10. As depicted, the apparent spatial distribution of the SMAP-GFMS correlation is not random but characterized by regional hot spots and cold spots, which reflect relatively strong and weak model and observation concurrence. Regional hot spots are observed over 37.6% of the global domain, including India, the Indochina Peninsula, and significant portions of Africa and Amazonia. Cold spots are apparent over 28.5% of the global domain including the eastern and mid-western United States, Europe, Central Africa, Arabian Peninsula, Southeast China, and Southeast Australia. This strong spatial pattern confirms that locations with both strong and weak SMAP-GFMS correlations are spatially clustered and likely influenced by regional gradients in influential environmental factors.

Many of the high SMAP-GFMS correlation areas correspond with documented flood events occurring during the observation period, including the California central valley and Southern USA (Brakenridge, 1996; Tellman et al., 2016). The area northeast of the Caspian Sea also shows high regional correlation; this area is arid but showed a strong SMAP F_w flood signal (Du et al., 2018), which is also confirmed in the independent GFMS record and caused by an excessive ENSO-driven precipitation driven flood event (Zhai et al., 2016). Additionally, the global pattern in correlation strength is inversely proportional to increasing SMAP F_w uncertainty under higher vegetation biomass levels, and may also be influenced by secondary noise factors such as complex topographic heterogeneity occurring below the resolution of the GFMS

Table 1

Summary of Pearson correlation analysis between GFMS runoff and SMAP F_w over the global domain.

	No. of cells (9 km by 9 km)	Min	Max	Q1	Median	Q3	Mean	Standard deviation
Pearson's r	1,165,517	-0.9928	0.9992	0.2602	0.5377	0.7342	0.4754	0.3212
Significance (p -value)	1,165,517	0.0000	1.0000	0.0132	0.1054	0.4310	0.2507	0.2967
Distance Correlation d_{cor}	1,165,517	0.0083	0.9979	0.1486	0.2508	0.4453	0.3180	0.2134

Fig. 6. The global distribution of r value categories (X-axis) describing relations between GFMS runoff and SMAP F_w by their relative frequency (Y-axis) expressed as a percent of global study domain.

model and SMAP sensor footprint. Generally greater L-band RFI can occur over more heavily populated urban zones resulting in greater SMAP T_b and F_w retrieval error (Du et al., 2018). Lower SMAP-GFMS correlations in the wet tropics are likely due to larger SMAP uncertainty in these areas due to the higher tropical forest biomass cover. The SMAP F_w retrievals likely have a wet bias due to difficulty in distinguishing between saturated surface soil and standing water. Lower SMAP-GFMS correlation areas may also reflect low characteristic seasonal climate and flood variability, including both arid desert and wet tropical locations. The relative influence of the five major environmental factors on the SMAP-GFMS global correlation pattern are examined below.

3.2. SMAP-GFMS correlation and Köppen climate zones

To evaluate climate and vegetation related impacts on SMAP-GFMS correspondence, the detailed Köppen classes were aggregated into more general categories, including: *Tropical Rainforest* and *Tropical Monsoon* (high vegetation), *Tropical Savannah* (low-moderate vegetation), *Temperate with Dry Season*, *Temperate without Dry Season*, *Arid*, *Cold*. *Polar* areas were excluded from the comparison due to the limited extent of these areas within the GFMS domain. The result is summarized in Fig. 11.

Overall, 63.9% of all available cells in the global study domain show moderate to strong correlations (i.e. $r \geq 0.4$); approximately 47.1% of these cells occur in tropical and arid climate zones, 10.9% in the temperate zone, and 5.6% in cold climate areas. Grid cells with correlations > 0.4 are generally observed in zones of *Arid* (26.5%) and *Tropical Savannah* (low-moderate vegetation) (13.0%) climates

(Fig. 11(a)). These areas have generally low to moderate vegetation cover and predominantly dry conditions, but also experience extreme precipitation events and transient flooding. The SMAP surface water retrievals show generally better retrieval accuracy in low to moderate vegetation conditions (Du et al., 2018), which may contribute to the stronger SMAP-GFMS correspondence in these dryland areas. Climates with the least percent of moderate-to-high correlation ($r \geq 0.4$) cells are observed in *Temperate with and without Dry Season* (11.0%) and *Cold* (5.6%) climate zones. Cells with negative SMAP-GFMS correlations ($r < 0$) represented $< 9.5\%$ of the global domain and were predominantly located in *Arid-Desert-Hot* (22.3%), *Temperate-Without Dry Season-Hot Summer* (13.6%), and *Arid-Steppe-Cold* (9.0%) climate zones.

When individual climate zones are considered, most grid cells with $r \geq 0.4$ are observed in *Tropical Savannah* (78.2%), *Tropical Rainforest and Monsoon* (74.7%), and *Temperate with Dry Season* (71.4%) climate categories (Fig. 11(b)); whereas *Cold* (49.8%) and *Temperate Without Dry Season* (46.2%) climate zones have the least percent of cells with $r \geq 0.4$. These results generally confirm (except for the *Tropical Rainforest and Monsoon* zone) that the SMAP-GFMS correlation is high in drier climate areas with high seasonal flood variability and low to moderate vegetation cover where the SMAP F_w retrievals have higher accuracy (Du et al., 2018).

3.3. SMAP-GFMS correlation and land cover

As illustrated in Fig. 12, globally the grid cells with $r \geq 0.4$ largely occur in *Barren or Sparsely Vegetated* land areas (10.7%), *Evergreen Broadleaf Forest* (9.2%), *Grasslands* (8.9%), *Open Shrublands* (7.7%) and

Fig. 7. The distribution of GFMS runoff and SMAP F_w correlations (r) where the monthly F_w record is temporally lagged by up to 7 months with respect to runoff. X: temporal lag (0 to 7 months), Y: percent of grid cells of the global domain with a certain correlation ($r \geq 0.4$ or $r \geq 0$).

(caption on next page)

Fig. 8. (a) Map showing highest per-cell correlation (r) between GFMS routed runoff and SMAP Fw, where the monthly Fw record is temporally lagged up to 3 months over the global GFMS domain (50°N to 50°S, and 180°W to 180°E). (b) Map of the significance (p -value) of the highest per-cell correlations between GFMS runoff and SMAP Fw, where the Fw record is shifted by up to 3 months over the GFMS domain. (c) The temporal lag (0, 1, 2, or 3 months) between GFMS runoff and SMAP Fw showing the highest correlation (r -value) at each grid cell. Masked areas outside of the classification domain or not meeting the comparison criteria and screened from the analysis are denoted as No Data (in grey) or shown in white.

Savannahs (6.5%). Most of these areas except for the forest category represent low to moderate vegetation cover and relatively dry climate zones. In contrast, areas with the least percent of $r \geq 0.4$ cells occur in *Urban and Built-up* area (0.1%), *Closed Shrubland* (0.1%) and *Permanent Wetlands* (0.3%). The lower SMAP-GFMS correspondence in these areas may reflect one or more contributing factors, including greater RFI contamination and associated SMAP retrieval uncertainty in urban areas, relatively low seasonal flood variability which can degrade correlation strength, and greater data gaps in areas with an extended frozen season which can also degrade the significance and strength of the correlations. Cells with negative SMAP-GFMS correspondence ($r < 0$) were primarily located in *Grasslands* (1.4%), *Croplands* (1.1%) and *Evergreen Broadleaf Forest* (1.0%).

When individual land cover types are considered, 85.0% of *Closed Shrubland* areas have moderate-to-high SMAP-GFMS correspondence ($r \geq 0.4$), followed by *Permanent Wetlands* (76.3%), *Savannahs* (72.9%), and *Woody Savannahs* (71.7%). *Urban and Built-up* lands have the lowest percentage of favorable ($r \geq 0.4$) correlations (47.8%), followed by *Mixed forest* (53.3%) and *Deciduous Broadleaf forest* (54.4%). *Urban and Built-up* lands have the most cells (19.2%) with $r < 0$, followed by *Mixed Forest* (16.7%). These results are generally consistent with the above climate analysis given the close relationship between climate and vegetation. These results also confirm generally stronger SMAP-GFMS correspondence in areas with low to moderate vegetation cover and away from urban areas and large water bodies where SMAP retrieval accuracy is generally greater (Du et al., 2018). Lower SMAP-GFMS correspondence also occurs in areas with an extended frozen season, where frozen conditions are excluded from the SMAP Fw retrievals, resulting in a shorter data record to support the correlation analysis. These areas include higher elevations and northern temperate forest, shrubland and grassland areas.

3.4. SMAP-GFMS correlation and the distribution of stream orders

Globally, for cells characterized by river orders 1, 2, 3 and 4, the most frequent r bin extends from $0.4 \leq r < 0.7$; and for cells with orders 5, 6, 7 and 8 the most frequent r bin is $r \geq 0.7$ (Fig. 13a). These results indicate that stronger SMAP-GFMS correlations ($r \geq 0.7$) are generally found in cells with larger rivers (stream orders 5, 6, 7 and 8).

In contrast, the majority of cells with $r < 0$ have the smallest stream orders 1 (5.87%) and 2 (2.05%), indicating less SMAP-GFMS consistency and more challenges faced by at least one of the two products in mountain top or headwater areas. Overall, grid cells with lower stream orders have more values in every r bin, which reflects the skewed geographical distribution of the orders. Similarly, 73% of the cells have an upstream flow accumulation area of $< 1000 \text{ km}^2$. Of these cells, almost half (46.5%) show moderate to strong SMAP-GFMS correlations ($r \geq 0.4$) as shown in Fig. 13a. However, the r values tend to be larger than 0.4 for cells with an accumulation area $> 100,000 \text{ km}^2$, with a negligible percent of cells having r values < 0.4 .

When individual Strahler orders are considered (Fig. 13b), for lower river orders 1, 2, 3 and 4, the percentage continues to increase with r bins until it drops at $r \geq 0.7$, while for higher orders 5, 6, 7, 8, the distribution of r values is monotonic with a peak at $r \geq 0.7$. The total percentage of grid cells with moderate-to-high r value ($0.4 \leq r < 0.7$ and $r \geq 0.7$) appears to be similar across river orders, i.e., order 3 (64.5%), 4 (64.2%), 1 (63.9%), 2 (63.8%), 5 (62.9%), 8 (61.4%), 6 (60.5%) and 7 (59.7%). However, the frequency of cells with high r value ($r \geq 0.7$) consistently increases as the river order gets higher. Overall, these results confirm that at different Strahler orders, SMAP and GFMS results are consistent at $r \geq 0.4$, but with better consistency for larger rivers (orders 5, 6, 7 and 8). Fig. 13b reflects the fact that hydrological models (e.g., DRIVE) tend to result in relatively better simulation of streamflow or routed runoff for downstream higher order river reaches compared to upstream lower order rivers. This pattern is consistent with observations of lower random error in satellite based area-averaged precipitation as the upstream river basin area increases (Nijssen and Lettenmaier, 2004; Nikolopoulos et al., 2010; Wu et al., 2014); whereas SMAP also shows better Fw performance in areas with a larger surface water proportion, consistent with higher order rivers.

The similar trends are also observed in flow accumulation. For watersheds exceeding $100,000 \text{ km}^2$, larger watershed sizes generally have more cells with higher r values; this relationship is also monotonic, with most cells having $r \geq 0.7$ (Fig. 14a). Smaller watersheds ($< 100,000 \text{ km}^2$) have a peak percentage of cells with intermediate SMAP-GFMS correlations ($0.7 > r \geq 0.4$). However, all watersheds tend to have more cells with moderate or high SMAP-GFMS correlation; e.g., when different r bins are considered, watersheds smaller than

Fig. 9. The monthly SMAP Fw and GFMS routed runoff and the temporal lag at (51.607W, 1.287S) which is also illustrated in the inset map in Fig. 4(c). To facilitate graphical illustration, the runoff data are normalized to values < 1 .

Fig. 10. Spatial distribution of the SMAP-GFMS correlation r . At 95% confidence level ($p < 0.05$), significant spatial clusters of high and low correlations are denoted as High-High (hot spots) and Low-Low (cold spots) area clusters, respectively; a high correlation area surrounded by relatively low r values is labeled as a High-Low cluster (spatial outlier), while a low r -value cluster surrounded by relatively high r values is labeled as a Low-High cluster (outlier).

500,000 km² have similar percentages of cells with $r \geq 0.4$ (63.6% for 0–999 km², 64.9% for 1000–9999 km², 64.4% for 10,000–99,999 km², 63.8% for 100,000–499,999 km²) (Fig. 14b). More than half (59.8%) of cells with $r \geq 0.4$ occur in watersheds larger than 500,000 km². Grid

cells with larger upstream drainage areas also tend to have stronger SMAP-GFMS correspondence ($r > 0.7$), which is also consistent with the Strahler Order based analysis.

Fig. 11. (a) The distribution of r -values by climate categories. X: r bins grouped by climate category, Y: the percentages are computed relative to all grid cells in the global study domain. (b) The distribution of r -values within each climate category. X: r bins grouped by climate category, Y: the percent of cells within each r bin in a climate category. For each climate category, the percentages within the r bins sum to 100%.

Fig. 12. The distribution of r by global land cover type. The percentages are computed relative to all grid cells in the global study domain. The labels are the percentages with $r \geq 0.4$ in each land cover type.

3.5. The SMAP-GFMS correlation and terrain

Globally, the SMAP-GFMS correlations were evaluated against their respective MRVBF class for each grid cell in the global domain (Fig. 15a). Cells with moderate-to-high SMAP-GFMS correspondence ($r \geq 0.4$) are generally associated with larger MRVBF class numbers (4.8% in class 1, to 13.7% in class 6). This indicates that cells in more extensive, low lying valley bottom locations tend to have better SMAP-GFMS correlation. Class 0 cells are generally associated with higher elevations and steeper slopes (e.g., mountains), which interestingly also have the second highest (next to class 6) percent of cells with $r \geq 0.4$ (12.0%). Within each class, the most frequent cells always have moderate SMAP-GFMS correlation ($0.4 \leq r < 0.7$), followed by strong ($r \geq 0.7$) and weak ($0 \leq r < 0.4$) correlations. These results indicate that there are always more cells having moderate to strong SMAP-GFMS correspondence in each MRVBF class.

When individual MRVBF classes are considered, the number of grid cells with $r \geq 0.4$ in different classes is very similar, ranging from 62.6% (Class 1) to 66.6% (Class 6); and the number of cells with $r \geq 0.7$

is between 27.4% (Class 1) and 32.6% (Class 6). Class 6 has the least number of cells with $r < 0$. All classes have a peak number of cells with moderate SMAP-GFMS correlation ($0.4 \leq r < 0.7$), followed by strong ($r \geq 0.7$) and weak ($0 \leq r < 0.4$) categories in relative importance (Fig. 15b). When cells are grouped into r bins (Fig. 15c), again Class 6 has the greatest proportion of cells with $r > 0$, indicating that this class carries the majority of cells with strong positive SMAP-GFMS correspondence. For each r bin, the percentage of cells with favorable correlation consistently increases at higher class numbers (i.e., flatter and lower). Class 0 carries 20% of cells with $r < 0$ and 38.5% of cells with $r \leq 0.4$, while Class 6 contains more cells with higher r values than the lower classes. These results indicate that the SMAP and GFMS model results tend to show higher correspondence in areas characterized by relatively flat and low lying terrain, with the strongest correlations occurring in large valley bottom locations (i.e. Class 6). This is reasonable since inundation tends to occur in relatively low and flat areas, even in highly elevated mountain or foothill regions.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 13. (a) Percentage of grid cells (relative to the global domain) with defined r value ranges (bins) in each Strahler order. (b) Percentage of each r bin within each Strahler stream order; X: r bins by Strahler order, Y: percentage of grid cells in each r bin and Strahler order, where the percentages in each order sum to 100%.

Fig. 14. (a) Percentage of grid cells (relative to global domain) organized by different r bins and five watershed size classes: 0–9999, 1000–9999, 10,000–99,999, 100,000–499,999, and $\geq 500,000$ km². (b) Percentage of grid cells with different SMAP-GFMS correlations by watershed size class, where the X-axis shows the correlation bins and the Y-axis denotes the percentage of grid cells in each r bin, where watershed size class is denoted by the different colors; the relative r bin proportions represented in each watershed size class sum to 100%.

Fig. 15. (a) Percentage (relative to global domain) of SMAP-GFMS r bins by MRVBF class, where r bins are denoted on the X-axis, MRVBF class is denoted by color, and r bin proportions are represented on the Y-axis. (b) The percentage of each r bin in an MRVBF class relative to all grid cells within the same class. Within each class, the total of the percentages for the r bins sum to 100%. (c) The percentage of each MRVBF class relative to all grid cells within the same bin. Within each bin, the total of the percentages for the r bins sum to 100%.

4. Discussion and conclusions

Improving hydrological model-based global flood information is crucial for real-time flood monitoring and early warning systems. This study evaluates GFMS model results using satellite low frequency microwave (L-band) observations of land surface water inundation dynamics from the NASA SMAP sensor. The SMAP fractional water cover (F_w) retrievals are used in this study for evaluating dynamic precipitation-driven GFMS runoff and surface water storage predictions. The SMAP F_w global record has mean 3-day temporal fidelity, favorable

global accuracy and moderate spatial resolution that provides a suitable observational benchmark to evaluate independent GFMS predictions derived primarily from satellite based precipitation inputs.

This study investigated the spatial and temporal consistency of SMAP and GFMS derived aggregate monthly surface water dynamics. Potential factors influencing SMAP and GFMS performance and their correlations were examined, including climate, land cover, watershed hydrology and terrain factors. The Pearson's correlation coefficient r was used as a metric to compare and quantify the correspondence between SMAP F_w and GFMS routed runoff patterns over the global GFMS

domain and initial period of SMAP operations (June 2015 to May 2016). Approximately 63.9% of the global domain showed moderate to strong, positive SMAP-GFMS correspondence ($r \geq 0.4$). These results indicate general spatial and seasonal consistency between GFMS hydrological model predictions driven by satellite precipitation observations and independent observations of surface water inundation dynamics from SMAP. The SMAP-GFMS global correlation patterns reveal regional zones of relatively strong agreement (hot spots) and much weaker correspondence (cold spots) that reflect clustering patterns of environmental and uncertainty factors influencing both SMAP Fw and GFMS performance.

The majority of areas with favorable SMAP-GFMS correspondence ($r \geq 0.4$) were in relatively dry climate zones with low to moderate vegetation cover. These areas also coincide with generally higher SMAP Fw retrieval accuracy (Du et al., 2018). Downstream areas of large river basins having higher Strahler stream orders (5, 6, 7 and 8) also have generally stronger SMAP-GFMS correlations, with stronger correspondence for grid cells associated with broad, low elevation valley bottom locations. These results imply greater SMAP-GFMS consistency in larger watersheds, which are better resolved by the coarse footprint satellite retrievals and model simulations. In contrast, densely populated urban areas tend to have lower SMAP-GFMS correlations, which may reflect lower SMAP Fw accuracy from RFI or lower GFMS accuracy due to water management practices that are not adequately represented in the DRIVE hydrological model.

The SMAP and GFMS derived monthly flood dynamics are temporally synchronous over 33.1% of the global domain, while up to a 3-month lag in the SMAP Fw retrievals are required for optimal correspondence with the GFMS flood predictions over 21% of the global domain. This lag effect is attributed to the fact that SMAP and GFMS utilize different modeling mechanisms and represent different aspects of flood information. The lag can also be due to shorter model residence time for water moving through river basins as a result of inappropriate parameterization of drainage network, relative coarse resolution precipitation input, or the biased high in inundation estimation by SMAP in area with saturated soil.

The results of this study indicate that GFMS and SMAP provide complementary information on surface water storage variations influencing precipitation driven runoff and flooding. SMAP and GFMS can be complementary to each other in those areas with weaker correspondence, particularly when one is of low quality, while the other is considered to be more reliable. SMAP is sensitive to area changes in surface water bodies that are linked with associated water storage changes due to management practices, which may complement GFMS when these storages aren't currently fully represented in the model; this may also partly account for some of the observed temporal lag effects in this study. Meanwhile, GFMS can provide helpful information in floodplain with heavy forest when SMAP has challenges in identifying water under trees. The above results offer a guideline documenting the accuracy and usability of GFMS global flood information in terms of SMAP data. Such consistency analysis can provide knowledge of the strength and limitation of both SMAP and GFMS, and thus potentially improve the model result based on the sources, patterns and driving factors of model uncertainty and consistency.

Future studies will include further comparisons over a longer SMAP operational data record, including the role of both surface water inundation and soil moisture related factors affecting runoff and flood risk. This study emphasized a seasonal assessment of aggregated monthly records. However, GFMS provides inundation and runoff predictions at a 3-hour time step while SMAP provides up to twice-daily Fw retrievals; these capabilities enable model and satellite assessments of more transient precipitation and flood response characteristics (Hostache et al., 2018; Revilla-Romero et al., 2016). This study also provides an initial step toward GFMS DRIVE model assimilation of satellite based water cover and soil moisture observations to enhance global flood predictions.

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